

INFLUENCE OF SCHOOL FEEDING PROGRAMME ON PUPILS' RETENTION RATE IN PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN RWANDA A CASE OF PRIMARY SCHOOLS OF BUGESERA DISTRICT

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10060354>

Published Date: 01-November-2023

Abstract: The research assessed the influence of school feeding programme on pupil retention rates in public primary schools in Rwanda. Specifically, we analysed the implementation of school feeding programme in public primary schools of Bugesera District, evaluated the level of pupil's retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District and determined the influence of school feeding programme on pupil's retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District. The sample size was 375, including 53 Teachers, 54 students, 3 Head teachers. Primary sources were gathered using questionnaires, interviews, and observation methods to triangulate the data. This study used purposive, stratified, and simple random sampling methods to derive a sample population from the respondents. The study applied both quantitative and qualitative methods complementarily in data collection and analysis. Content analysis helped qualitative data analysis, and quantitative data was presented using the statistical package for social sciences by descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (correlational and regression analysis). For the first objective, results indicated that that 59.3% strongly agreed that The school has frequent discussions on the topic of school food in order to identify problems and devise solutions, 58.3% strongly agreed that The school has made a school feeding committee to ensure quality and safety of food before procurement, when receiving, during storage, cooking and serving, 63.7% that There is a follow up of how the suppliers bring foods on time, , 68.9% agreed that The hygiene of room is ensured before pupils are served the meal, 55.6% agreed that The teacher's guide learners to take care of gardens of vegetables in extra curricula activities hours. This indicated there is implementation of school feeding programs. Results on the influence of school feeding programme on pupil's retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District indicated that most measures were positively associated with each other. Since the degree of significance was less than 0.05, in conclusion, the study shows that most commonly, school activities such as Food and timing of meal, Food quality and quantity as well as Food nutritional value have the same attitude on pupils' retention rate in public primary schools in Rwanda. The research revealed Increased promotion, High completion rate for both girls and boys as well as High rate of Attractiveness show pupils' retention rate in public primary schools in Rwanda. Finally, the above factors have a positive association with pupils' retention rate in public primary schools in Rwanda since the p-value was less than 0.05. Recommended that Rwandan government should provide enough resources and materials to support the implementation of school feeding programme to all school and encourage the parents to be involve in that programme and The school staff teacher and Headteacher must work to gether to help in smooth implementation of this programme by helping the children and help in preparing a well quality and quantity food and also mut be given training on how to prepare a diet food.

Keywords: Food, Food nutrition, School feeding, student retention.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background of the study

Worldwide, All UN member states strive to overcome the obstacles posed by the forces that have pushed globalization, which led to the creation of the MDGs in the year 2000. As mentioned in MDG Number 1: Eradicate Extreme Yearning and Destitution, concern was given to hunger and dependence in the MDG strategy. Thus, the established objective becomes: the continuous 2015 extent of individuals who experience the ill effects of craving is split when contrasted with 1990 (UNO, 2005). School encouraging projects constitute basic mediations that were presented in various created and creating nations of the world to address the issues of neediness, increase enrollment in schools, and enhance student performance.

In our eastern African region, In Kenya, the UNESCO (1990) meeting revealed that the Government had numerous long stretches of involvement in running projects that address instructive issues, for example, the wellbeing needs of school-age kids, including approaches, stretched-out access to various levels of tutoring, and school-encouraging projects by networks and the government in dry and semi-dry zones (Bright Hope, 2012).

Along with other initiatives, the United Republic of Tanzania's government was given Dodoma, Arusha, Singida, Bunda, Musoma, and Manyara school feeding programs to implement in partnership with the World Food Program in some areas where food security looked to be a concern in 2000. The Sustenance for Education program was gone for expanding youngsters entrance to training and enhancing the nature of that instruction, incrementing understudies' enlistment, participation, and focus traverse among Students and their learning limits, and lessening dropout rates and sexual orientation divergence in grade schools. Region Governments of Rural People Group were prepared to give day-by-day school suppers, increment the limit of Village Councils and School Committees to distinguish and deliver obstructions to access to class for young ladies and young men, and assemble networks to contribute time, reserves, and in-kind products to effectively take an interest in all parts of the program (URT, 2013).

Rwanda, on August 17, 2012, executed a school feeding program after a pilot visit to Brazil. The WFP Center of Excellence against Hunger went to Rwanda to catch up on April's investigation visit. The administration of Rwanda and the meeting designation made up of delegates from the Center of Excellence, FNDE, and ABC concurred on various proposed stages to actualize the national school encouraging system. Nowadays, the nation has three active school feeding programs, two of which are run and sponsored by the government. One is the school milk program known as "one cup of milk per child", which is supported by MINAGRI. This initiative provides milk twice a week to students in grades 1-3 of pre-primary and elementary schools. Initiative for Secondary School Nutrition Kindergarten and elementary school students assisted by this program receive milk twice a week in grades 1-3. Next, there is the Secondary School Feeding Initiative, a MINEDUC-funded initiative that pays for meals prepared at secondary schools.

Problem Statement

School attendance and students' retention are practical education problems in developing countries, including Rwanda. Both school attendance and student retention affect the education sector. Hunger is among the factors that contribute to the increased dropout rate, poor performance, truancy, and gender disparity among school-age children (URT, 2014). This challenge is noted in the region as one of the issues for improving students' retention at school.

There are some reasons that lead to increased problems, including those that emanate from society, such as poverty, the environment, attitudes toward formal education, and others. Some efforts have been made by the government to improve the situation in order to reduce the problem. This effort is partly supported by the government through the Ministry of Education, and the other part is accomplished by the parents of students.

Although many researchers have addressed school feeding programs, they have not paid attention to the influence of school feeding programs on students' retention rates in public primary schools. Therefore, this is the knowledge gap that the researcher needs to fill. This study investigated the influence of school feeding programs on students' retention rates in public secondary schools. Based on this context, the investigator was instructed to conduct this specific study to examine the extent to which school feeding programs contribute to students' retention in schools in Bugesera District, Rwanda. The findings of this study, therefore, were to provide facts in a deeper sense to all education stakeholders.

Objectives of the study

The research identified two kinds of objectives: general objectives and specific objectives.

General objective of the study

The main objective of this research was to assess the influence of school feeding programme on pupil retention rates in public primary schools in Rwanda.

Specific objectives

- i. To analyse the implementation of school feeding programme in public primary schools of Bugesera District.
- ii. To evaluate the level of pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District.
- iii. To determine the influence of school feeding programme on pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District.

Research questions

- i. What are the main challenges of school feeding programme in selected public primary schools of Bugesera District ?
- ii. What is the level of students retention in selected public primary schools of Bugesera District ?
- iii. What is the influence of school feeding programme on students retention rate in selected public primary schools of Bugesera District ?

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE**Theoretical Literature**

The school feeding program originated in the 1930s, when feeding programs were launched in England as well as the United States of America (USA) main goal of enhancing learners' progress by offering them (Ritcher et al, 2000). School feeding and food provision (SFFP) in schools began in Brazil following World War II in 1945 (Swartz, 2015). Brazil controlled a decentralization approach as a policy to operate the program during its execution. Brazil also established local meals councils, which comprised the government, school officials, educators, parents, and civil society groups (WFP, 2012).

South Africa also offered free milk, fortified biscuits, and nutritional supplementation for both caloric and white students (Tomlinson, 2012). The Malawi feeding program, known as Food for Education (FFE), was founded to alleviate short-term starvation while also improving desired overall academic achievements in order to promote school enrollment, attendance, and learning potential. In Malawi, a nation the project targeted low-income pupils, notably girls, orphaned, and kids who were vulnerable (Swartz, 2015). The World Food Assistance Program reports that the school feeding program in Zimbabwe was carried out in collaboration with various Ministries such as the WFP, the Ministry of Education, Sport, and Culture, the Ministry of Health and Child Welfare, as well as charitable groups including Catholic Relief Services, World Vision, and Care International. Taking action aimed to give hands to children in lower primary school grades, including those who were unable to attend school owing to their vulnerability as orphans and other vulnerable children. During break time, these students were given corn meal porridge (WFP, 2009).

Empirical literature**An examination of the implementation of the school nutrition program in elementary schools owned by municipalities**

Many nutrition research have demonstrated that undernutrition impedes children's physical and cognitive growth, hence establishing a relationship between nourishment and academic achievement (Alabi, 2013). Despite the fact that food has generally been considered merely a source of energy and building materials for the body, a new study has offered interesting evidence for the impact of dietary variables on mental performance. Children are not only encouraged to go to school, but their food status, cognitive development, and academic success are all significantly influenced by this as well. According to the literature, the quality and nutritious components of meals influence the growth and learning capability of the recipients (Jukes et al, 2018). Nutrition and health status have a significant impact on a child's learning and performance in school. Children who do not consume enough of a certain nutrient in their diet do not learn as well as children who are healthy and

well-nourished. Children who struggle with their cognition and their senses are less likely to achieve success naturally and are far more inclined to receive recurrent levels. One of the major causes of low performance is inconsistent school attendance among hungry and sick youngsters (Uduku, 2013). Children who participate in school feeding programs have the potential to perform better since it enables them to attend class regularly and learn more effectively, according to (Yunusa, 2012).

In a research conducted in Jamaica, he discovered that when students in Grade 2 began being fed at school, they performed better in Arithmetic. However, the influence of the School Feeding Program on students' academic achievement has been met with conflicting opinions. The influence of SFPs on academic achievement is uneven and relies on a number of variables within the setting in which the program is administered, despite the fact that they motivate parents to register their children in school. This led Uduku (2011) to draw the conclusion that the best use of SFPs would be in conjunction with appropriate learning resources, physical facilities, and instructor motivation.

The Evaluation level of pupils retention rate in selected public primary schools

World Food Programme conducted a survey on thirty-two Sub-Saharan African countries in which it targeted 4,175 schools assisted by their programme in food provision to approximately 21.7 million children ; the study indicated an annual rise of 14% in enrolment of school for children (Gelli, 2013). Gelli (2013) discovered that, in only one year, the Food for Education (FFE) project raised absolute enrollment at schools funded by the World Food Programme (WFP) by 22% and 28% for boys and girls, respectively. However, following the first year, variations were noticed on the patterns of enrollment which were majorly due to the type of FFE program implemented. The two types of FFE programmes included : a combination of rations to take home and school-provided meals, as well as school-provided food alone. In the next year, there was a 30% rise in enrolment among females in schools that supplied both meals at school and take-home rations, while enrollment remained unchanged in schools that solely provided food at school. The U.N. also noted that increasing primary school participation in 32 countries by giving kids take-home ratios in addition to school meals benefited girls most of all (WFP, 2016).

In Malawi, a three-month experiment of a school feeding program was performed to assess its influence on student enrolment and attendance. When comparing the treatment group to the control group over the same period, the study discovered a five percent rise in enrolment and a thirty-six percent improvement in attendance (WFP, 2015). A study conducted by Yendaw and Dayour (2015) sought to assess the impact of the national school feeding program on the enrollment and retention of students in Ghana, where enrollments were examined by comparing two periods in which children were enrolled by their parents Before and following the commencement of the school food program. According to their findings, enrolment was 35.8% prior to the implementation of the SFP but increased dramatically to 64.2% afterward (Yendaw & Dayour, 2015).

A WFP assessment on the school enrolment rate in Rwanda found that enrollment increased from 77% in 2010 to 97% in 2015, partly due to the implementation of free primary education and partly due to the provision of school meals (WFP, 2016).

The most disadvantaged girls nevertheless come to class and bring hungry children to school every day, despite the tight gender parity in schools with feeding programs. According to a research done in 2017 by Kremer and Miguel, "School Feeding Programme decreases the net cost of taking children to school specifically in big families thus boosting education enrollment." Finan (2012) stated that food serves as a potent inducement for enrolling kids. Different schools' enrollments have been seen to gradually rise.

The Influence of a school food program on student retention in a sample of public primary Schools

Since its inception, the School Food Program has risen substantially student attendance in schools across the world (UNESCO, 2007). Randomized studies have demonstrated that SFP enhances student attendance (WFP, 2016).

According to Del Rosso (2013), feeding children is a powerful motivator for them to go to school on a regular basis. Girls have benefited the most from SFP in many communities since they are culturally impoverished in most households, although male children are usually given more options to attend school in such difficult circumstances. SFP has assisted parents in saving money by eating less food and allowing girls to attend school (WFP, 2016). Students in Bangladesh increased their attendance by 20% and decreased their nonparticipation by 2% as a result of the establishment of a school-based feeding program in their schools (Ahmed & Del-Ninno, 2013). Successful schools started by engaging students and making sure

they came to school on a regular basis (Ahmed & Del-Ninno, 2013). When compared to schools without school feeding programs, attendance in schools with SFPs was 12% higher (70% for schools with SFPs versus 58% for schools without the program). As a result, dropout rates were shown to be 9% lower in SFP-administered schools than in those without (Ahmed & Del-Ninno, 2013). According to Gilligan (2009), school feeding programs have had a big influence on students' attendance and involvement in class. Ahmed and Del-Ninno (2013) shown that the program had a statistically important beneficial effect on pupils' school attendance in Bangladesh. According to him, the initiative has boosted students' monthly attendance in class by 1.34 days (Ahmed & Del Ninno, 2013).

Theoretical framework

There were several theories on the dropout phenomenon, each with its own set of circumstances that encourage kids to stay in school. Socioeconomic status, culture, parental or community involvement, and educational policy are examples of such influences. This was primarily a discussion of three major ideas that are associated with education, notably the Maslow, Vroom, and Epstein theories.

Maslow Theory

The hierarchy of needs theory developed by Abraham Maslow in 1954 served as the foundation for the study, which contends that if basic wants are met, people may express more specific requests. He propose the well-known self-actualization paradigm, which is a hierarchy of needs. Following these basic needs (food, shelter, and clothing), there are other equally important wants (safety, love, self-esteem, and self-actualization). The three basic needs are clothing, food, and shelter. Maslow argue that if a person's basic needs are not met, they will spend time and energy trying to fulfill them, frequently at the expense of important requirements for growth and self-actualization. Hierarchically, the prerequisites are satisfied. This shows that people give priority to basic needs initially before turning their focus to more specific ones. Students won't be able to fulfill their potential and participate in their education if they are lacking in basic necessities, as food in this study.

The motivational Vroom Expectancy Theory.

This analysis was guided by the Vroom expectation theory of motivation, which was put forth by Vroom (1964) and Epstein. According to the Vroom expectancy theory of motivation, the degree of propensity to behave in a certain way depends on the degree of expectation that the performance will be followed by a given consequence and on the attractiveness of the outcome to the individual. Although Tolman associated learning with reinforcement, he did not believe that reinforcement was a necessary precondition for learning to occur. The goal of encouraging students who have experienced hunger and malnutrition to continue their studies is to lessen their hunger pangs.

Epstein Theory

Epstein's three realms of impact theory : school, family, and community. It focuses on establishing partnerships, linkages, and recognizing the overlap of different domains. These three major situations in which children learn and grow will be identified by this theory. Schools may either communicate extremely successfully in order to reach out to Families and the community can work separately, or they can create effective channels for interaction and communication to bridge the gap between the two.

Conceptual framework

This section has three divisions including independent, intervening and dependent variables

Independent variables

Dependent variable

Intervening variable

Figure 2. 1: Conceptual framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design.

According to Alvi (2016), a descriptive study is a plan that collects information at a specific location with the goal of defining various types of previous conditions, identifying principles against which those previous conditions are compared, and determining the correlation between specific events. This descriptive research methodology was chosen since it was facilitate quickly obtaining data from a large number of instances. It was entail the collecting of information from a sample of instructors, students, parents, and head teachers through the use of surveys, and it will explain events, arrange, tabulate, and show the variables.

To collect data, a descriptive and correlation research using a hybrid methodology was performed. This is because it allows for the collection of data regarding people's attitudes, points of view, or any number of different educational or societal problems. According to Babbie (2011). This study was seeking to accomplish the goal of a descriptive research, which was to identify the who, what, why, where, and how of the variables.

Target population

This section describes the study's sample size and sampling procedure as follows: Cooper et al. (2016) define the population as the complete collection of elements from which the research seeks to draw conclusions. This study's population consisted of 5544 respondents (composed of both parents and teachers) from Bugesera District's selected primary schools, such as Groupe Scolaire Nyakayaga, Groupe Scolaire Rutonde, and Groupe Scolaire Ruhuha.

Sample design

This section describes the study's sample size and sampling procedure as follows :

Sample Size

The used formula was invented by Taro Yamane (1967) which is $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$

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therefore for this study; $n = \frac{5544}{1+5544(0.05)^2} = n = \frac{5544}{1+5544(0.05)^2} = 375.302$ respondents, and then the sample is 375 participants, who were selected through simple random sampling techniques.

Where n is the intended sample size, e represents the likelihood of error (0.05 for 95% confidence level), and N represents the population size estimate.

Table 3.1: Sample Size

Names of Schools	Target Population	Sample Size
Teachers	54	47
Head Teachers	3	3
Parents	5434	325
Total	5544	375

Source : Primary Data (2023)

Sampling technique

Sampling is the process of removing a sufficient number of elements from a population. (Sekaran, 2005). In this investigation, a simple random sampling procedure was used to ensure that each participant had an equal and independent probability of participating in the study. This means that the total number of respondents was 5 444, with 53 instructors, 54 students, 3 principals, 5 437 parents, and a sample size of 375.

4. FINDINGS, INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION

The analysis on the implementation of school feeding programme in public primary schools of Bugesera District

The research identified the analyse towards the implementation of school feeding programme in public primary schools of Bugesera District, Rwanda. The following tables show how the participants Respond to the following statments.

Table 4. 5 teachers perception on the implementation of school feeding programme in public primary schools of Bugesera District

Statements	Strongly Disagree				Disagree				Neutral				Agree				Strongly Agree		Total	
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	Mean	Sd		
A teacher helps school contribution fees collection from parents to be well submitted at school.	2	4.4	5	11.1	3	6.7	9	20.0	26	57.8	43	1.484	1.223							
Teachers do a follow up when pupils are eating in their rooms	2	4.4	2	4.4	4	8.9	10	22.2	27	60.0	43	1.71	1.100							
The hygiene of room is ensured before pupils are served the meal	1	2.2	1	2.2	2	4.4	10	22.2	31	68.9	43	1.46	.868							
The teachers participate in food delivery to learners when the bell is rung for lunch time.	4	1.9	2	4.2	2	4.2	7	15.6	30	66.7	43	1.46	.868							
The teachers guide learners to take care of gardens of vegetales in extra curriculla activities hours	1	2.2	3	6.7	1	2.2	15	33.3	25	55.6	43	1.66	.977							

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Results in Table 4.5 evidenced responses on the perception of teachers perception on the implementation of school feeding programme in public primary schools of Bugesera District. Accordingly 28 (57.8%) Teachers strongly agreed that A teacher helps school contribution fees collection from parents to be well submitted at school, 27(60.0%) Teachers strongly agreed that Teachers do a follow up when pupils are eating in their rooms, 31(68.9%) Teachers strongly agreed that The hygiene of room is ensured before pupils are served the meal, 30(66.7%) Teachers strongly agreed that The teachers participate in food delivery to learners when the bell is rung for lunch time, 25(55.6%) Teachers strongly agreed that The teachers guide learners to take care of gardens of vegetales in extra curriculla activities hours., 31(68.9%) Teachers strongly agreed that A teacher helps school contribution fees collection from parents to be well submitted at school. This means that due to the view of the respondants accepted that Food and timing of meal, Food quality and quantity and Food nutritional value indicate school feeding programme implementation. According to the Ministry of Education Strategy Center (2018), develop school food programs because most students originate from low-income homes who do not have meals; this may also assist reduce absenteeism. Political commitment to school lunch programs is a prevalent strong trait in the region. Most nations have taken a rights-based approach to school meals and are on their way to achieving universal coverage at the primary school level. However, in some nations, rules are still fragmented or insufficient, and full compliance with standards and guidelines by all parties remains difficult. Governments have also shown a great financial commitment to school meals, making significant efforts to increase the scope of their programs. However, maintaining appropriate financing and providing excellent services all year round remains difficult for many countries (WFP, 2017).

Table 4. 6 parents 's Perception towards the implementation of school feeding programme in public primary schools of Bugesera District

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Total				
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	Mean	Sd			
The school has frequent discussions on the topic of school food in order to identify problems and devise solutions	10.3	1	25.7	2	12.3	1	37.8	3	25.8	192	59.3	329	1.69	329	
The school has made a school feeding committee to ensure quality and safety of food before procurement, when receiving, during storage, cooking and serving	8.2	1	25.8	2	16.4	1	49.1	3	31.8	189	58.3	329	1.58	.887	
There is a follow up of how the suppliers bring foods on time	16.4	1	9.8	1	2.5	0	86.3	6	26.5	206	63.6	329	1.58	1.017	
The report of the record of all food coming and going out of the storeroom is regularly well checked.	4.2	1	1.2	0	8.2	1	98.3	30	30.2	210	64.8	324	1.43	.72	
Resolutions and minutes of School Procurement Committee meetings are available	4.2	1	12.3	1	3.7	0	4.1	1	118.3	36.4	186	57.4	324	1.549	.802

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Data presented in Table 4.6, 192 (59.3%) parents strongly agreed that The school has frequent discussions on the topic of school food in order to identify problems and devise solutions, 189 (58.3%) parents strongly agreed that The school has made a school feeding committee to ensure quality and safety of food before procurement, when receiving, during storage, cooking and serving, 206(63.7%) parents strongly agreed that There is a follow up of how the suppliers bring foods on time, 210(64.8%) parents strongly agreed that The report of the record of all food coming and going out of the storeroom is regularly well checked, 19(67.9%) parents strongly agreed that Resolutions and minutes of School Procurement Committee meetings are available. From the response of the parents Also the high numbers of parents proved that in Bugesera District they are school feeding program implementation.the reseach done by (Marisennayya, 2023) On the effects of the School Feeding Program on Students' academic achievement by comparing beneficiary School feeding with non – beneficiaries of School feeding in SNNPR Wolaita Zone. The result indicated that,in the standardized exam, pupils from benefiting schools wrote 8.6 words per minute whereas students from non-benefiting schools wrote 6.16. It suggested that beneficiaries wrote more words than non-beneficiaries in school. Additionally, the School Feeding Programs had a statistically significant and favorable influence on kids' academic performance markers, such as average test scores, mother tongue reading progress, and mother tongue writing development, according to the independent sample t-test.

The level of pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District

This study evaluated the level of pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District, Rwanda, as presented in the following tables.

Table 4.7 Teachers perception on the level of pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Total	
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	Mean	Sd
The pupils are attracted to enroll because of free food at school for those who don't have regular food at home	28.3	5	20.8	0	0.7	0	29.2	10	41.7	24	2.25	1.42
Pupils pay attention and concentrate in learning because of school feeding program	28.3	0	0.0	0	0.6	0	25.0	16	66.7	24	1.58	1.138
The pupils get success and be promoted due to continuous school feeding program	28.3	0	0.0	0	0.2	0	8.3	20	83.3	24	1.50	1.21
The learners are motivated to learning due to the food they get at school	14.2	1	4.2	4	1.2	6	25.0	15	62.5	24	1.62	1.05

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Information depicted in Table 4.7, 10 (41.7%) Teachers strongly agreed that the pupils are attracted to enroll because of free food at school for those who don't have regular food at home while 7(29.2%) Teachers agreed with this statment, 16 (66.7%) Teachers strongly agreed that Pupils pay attention and concentrate in learning because of school feeding program. Additionally, 15(62.5%) Teachers strongly agreed that The learners are motivated to learning due to the food they get at school. From this above result indicated that they are school rentation rate in bugesera district schools due to high numbers of them as respodants accepted that as indicated in above table 4.7. (Malila, 2015) made research on showed that School feeding programs significantly improve students' learning styles. It is one of the most important strategies for encouraging learning to learners who are food insecure. This can drive students to concentrate and study more effectively, hence improving their learning capacity and performance. As a result, it is clear that providing meals to learners in primary schools boosted school attendance and reduced dropout among learners in Tanzanian community schools.

Table 4. 8 Head Teachers' perception on the level of pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District

Statments	Strongly Disagree				Disagree				Neutral				Agree				Strongly Agree				Total	N	Mean	Sd
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N								
The pupils are attracted to enroll because of free food at school for those who don't have regular food at home	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	33.3	266.7	3	1.33	.577									
High completion rate for both girls and boys are due to school feeding program	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	33.3	266.7	3	1.33	.577										
The pupils get success and be promoted due to continuous school feeding program	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3100.0	3	1.000	.000										
The learners are motivated to learning due to the food they get at school.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	66.7	133.3	3	1.66	.577											

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Results presented in Table 4.8, 66.7% Head teachers strongly agreed The pupils are attracted to enroll because of free food at school for those who don't have regular food at home, 66.7% Head teachers strongly agreed that High completion rate for both girls and boys are due to school feeding program while 33.3% Agreed with the statments Additionally, 100% Head teachers strongly agreed that The pupils get success and be promoted due to continuous school feeding program. In the same vein, 66.6% Head teachers strongly agreed that The learners are motivated to learning due to the food they get at school. From the respondants as Headteachers proved that in Bugesera District they are school rentention rate as indicated in above table. (Maijo, 2022) was carried out the research and evaluated the influence of a school feeding program on students' academic performance in Mlunduzi ward, Tanzania. This study employed a cross-sectional survey approach. This research was both qualitative and quantitative in character. A questionnaire was distributed to 96 respondents in four randomly selected elementary schools in Mlunduzi ward to assess the impact. To supplement the surveys, a focus group discussion (FGD) was conducted. During the focus group discussion, a checklist was utilized to evaluate data from learners and teachers. The findings suggest that the school feeding program had a substantial influence on students' academic achievement. According to the findings, the school feeding program improved test results, assisted in getting students into school, and improved overall academic achievement.

and timing of meal and vice versa. The research done by (Bekidusa, 2020) on The effect of a school feeding program on learner retention in Kenya's public primary indicated that schools School feeding programs influence learner retention in public primary schools with a reliability value of 0.8, which is considered minimally acceptable, rejecting the null hypothesis and implying that school feeding programs have a significant effect on learner retention in public primary schools. Learners involved in the school feeding programme has access to enhancing their academic performance since it enabled them to attend school frequently and learn more efficiently (Yunusa et al., 2012). Meyers et al. (2013) established that children from elementary schools who participated in school breakfast programme had shown significant growth in academic function.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

This section discussed the findings in accordance with three subsections based on research specific objectives as follows: To analyse the implementation of school feeding programme in public primary schools of Bugesera District, to evaluate the level of pupil's retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District, to determine the influence of school feeding programme on pupil's retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District, in Rwanda.

The implementation of school feeding programme in public primary schools as Secondary Schools Objective

The parents perception the Results indicated that 59.3% parents strongly agreed that The school has frequent discussions on the topic of school food in order to identify problems and devise solutions, 58.3% parents strongly agreed that The school has made a school feeding committee to ensure quality and safety of food before procurement, when receiving, during storage, cooking and serving, 63.7% parents strongly agreed that There is a follow up of how the suppliers bring foods on time, while on the teachers perception the the result indicated that 57.8% Teachers strongly agreed that A teacher helps school contribution fees collection from parents to be well submitted at school, 60.0% Teachers strongly agreed that Teachers do a follow up when pupils are eating in their rooms, 68.9% Teachers strongly agreed that The hygiene of room is ensured before pupils are served the meal, 30(66.7%) Teachers strongly agreed that The teachers participate in food delivery to learners when the bell is rung for lunch time, 55.6% Teachers strongly agreed that The teachers guide learners to take care of gardens of vegetables in extra curricula activities hours.

The level of pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District

This research analyzed the level the level of pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District.

Results discussed in chapter four indicated that 41.7% Teachers strongly agreed that the pupils are attracted to enroll because of free food at school for those who don't have regular food at home while 29.2% Teachers agreed with this statement, 66.7% Teachers strongly agreed that Pupils pay attention and concentrate in learning because of school feeding program. Additionally, 62.5% Teachers strongly agreed that The learners are motivated to learning due to the food they get at school.

Results in the perception of headteachers indicated that , 66.7% Head teachers strongly agreed The pupils are attracted to enroll because of free food at school for those who don't have regular food at home, 66.7% Head teachers strongly agreed that High completion rate for both girls and boys are due to school feeding program while 33.3% Agreed with the statements Additionally, 100% Head teachers strongly agreed that The pupils get success and be promoted due to continuous school feeding program. In the same vein, 66.6% Head teachers strongly agreed that The learners are motivated to learning due to the food they get at school.

The influence between school feeding programme and pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District.

The correlation and regression results established the existence of positive correlation between the schoolfeeding programmes and pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District where the p-value and significance were justified by the p-value which were less than 0.05, the study evidenced a positive correlation between school feeding programme on pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District.

Conclusions

Reconsidering findings from this present research, it concludes : To the first research objectives, the study reveals that The school has frequent discussions on the topic of school food in order to identify problems and devise solutions, The

school has made a school feeding committee to ensure quality and safety of food before procurement, when receiving, during storage, cooking and serving. There is a follow up of how the suppliers bring foods on time. A teacher helps school contribution fees collection from parents to be well submitted at school. Teachers do a follow up when pupils are eating in their rooms. The hygiene of room is ensured before pupils are served the meal. The teachers participate in food delivery to learners when the bell is rung for lunch time, as well as. The teachers guide learners to take care of gardens of vegetables in extra curricula activities hours.

The researcher reveals that The pupils are attracted to enroll because of free food at school for those who don't have regular food at home. High completion rate for both girls and boys are due to school feeding program. The pupils get success and be promoted due to continuous school feeding programme and The learners are motivated to learning due to the food they get at school. Pupils pay attention and concentrate in learning because of school feeding program

Results from objective three reveal that school feeding programme on pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District and were positively and statistically correlated since most of their level of significance level were more 0.05 in association with pupils retention rate in public primary schools of Bugesera District, Rwanda.

Recommendations

Reconsidering concluding remarks from the study findings and information argued that the author attempted to make some recommendations to the study.

Rwandan government recommended to provide enough resources and materials to support the implementation of school feeding programme to all school and encourage the parents to be involve in that programme.

The school staff teacher and Headteacher must work together to help in smooth implementation of this programme by helping the children and help in preparing a well quality and quantity food and also must be given training on how to prepare a diet food.

Suggestions for Further Studies

The study recommends future researches to carry out studies in the following subject: The impact of school feeding program on student academic performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ahmed, A. U. (2014). The Impact of a Food-For-Education Program Using Locally Produced Food on Sub-Saharan African Farmers and Consumers. *Washington, DC : International Research Food Policy Institute*
- [2] Ahmed, and M. Arnds-Kuenning (2016). Do crowded classrooms impede learning? Evidence from the Food for Education Program in Bangladesh. *Worlddevelopment, no. 34, p. 665.*
- [3] Bala, M., (2016). Methods for Teaching Children with Disabilities. *New International Ltd., New Delhi.*
- [4] BOdero.O. A (2015). In Nyanza, the adequacy and utilization of teaching resources for learners with slow learning abilities. *Unreleased Medical Project. Kenyatta University is located in Nairobi, Kenya.*
- [5] Reezigi. A and Pul. L(2021). Attitudes of Teachers and Students. *School Misbehavior As A Reaction To Teachers' Reduced Effort And Effect.*
- [6] Rumberger. W (2018). The Effects of Alternative Food for Education Programs on Academic Achievement and Cognitive Development in Northern Uganda, *International Food Policy Research Institute, mimeo. DC stands for Washington, DC. Rustermier,*
- [7] Temple .M and Walkley. G (2019). Nutrition Policies in Developing Countries: Problems and Opportunities. *International Food Policy Research Institute, Washington, DC.*
- [8] Tinto. Y (2015). Insights from Ghana and South Africa on School Building Design for Feeding Programs and Community Outreach. *The International Journal of Educational Development.*